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Abstract:

Let G be a graph and let v be any vertex of G . The open neighbourhood of a vertex $v \in V$ is defined as $N(v) = \{u \in V / uv \in E\}$, that is, the set of vertices adjacent to v . Then the neighbourhood contracted graph G_v of G , with respect to the vertex v is the graph with the vertex set $V - N(v)$, where two vertices u, w are adjacent in G_v if either $w = v$ and u is adjacent to any vertex of $N(v)$ in G or $u, w \notin N[v]$ and u, w are adjacent in G . In this paper, we prove some results on neighbourhood contraction of some special families of graphs. Also we construct n non isomorphic graphs with isomorphic neighbourhood contracted graph.

Key Words: Neighbourhood Contraction, Splitting Graph & Cosplitting Graph.

1. Introduction:

The graphs considered in this paper are finite, undirected and connected. Unless or otherwise stated, we consider only simple graphs. For notations and basic definitions, we refer [2]. Let $G(V, E)$ be a graph. Order of G is denoted by $n(G)$. A full vertex v is a vertex which is adjacent to every other vertices in G . That is, v is a full vertex, if $d(v) = n(G) - 1$. Distance between any two vertices u and v in a graph G is the length of a shortest path between them. It is denoted by $d(u, v)$. The neighbourhood of a vertex $v \in V$ is defined as $N(v) = \{u \in V / uv \in E\}$, that is, the set of vertices adjacent to v is called the neighbourhood of a vertex v . Or, more precisely, $N(v) = \{x \in V / d(x, v) = 1\}$ in G . In general, $N_k(v)$ is defined as $N_k(v) = \{u \in V(G) / d(u, v) = k\}$, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. For a subset V_1 of V , the induced subgraph induced by V_1 is denoted by $G[V_1]$. A clique C is a subset of vertices such that $G[C]$ is complete. The clique number $\omega(G)$ of a graph G is the number of vertices in a maximum clique in G . The corona $G_1 \circ G_2$ of two graphs G_1 and G_2 is defined as the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 which has p_1 vertices and p_1 copies of G_2 and then joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 to all the vertices in the i^{th} copy of G_2 . The concept of neighbourhood contraction was introduced by S.S. Kamath and Prameela Kolake[3]. The Neighbourhood contracted graph G_v of G , with respect to the vertex v is the graph with the vertex set $V - N(v)$, where two vertices $u, w \in V - N(v)$ are adjacent in G_v such that one of the following conditions holds:

1. $w = v$ and u is adjacent to any vertex of $N(v)$ in G .
2. $u, w \notin N[v]$ and u, w are adjacent in G .

For example, the graph G_{v_1} of G is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

The concept of splitting graph was introduced by Sampath Kumar and Walikar[4]. The graph $S(G)$ obtained from G by adding a new vertex w for every vertex $v \in V$ and joining w to all vertices adjacent to v in G is called the splitting graph of G . For example, a graph G and its splitting graph $S(G)$ are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

When we contract a vertex v in a splitting graph $S(G)$, the resultant graph is denoted by $[S(G)]_v$. Note that $S(G_v)$ denotes the splitting graph of the contracted graph G_v of G . For example, the graph G_{v_1} , $S(G_{v_1})$ and $[S(G)]_{v_1}$ for the graph in Figure 2 are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

The concept of cosplitting graph $CS(G)$ was introduced by Selvam Avadayappan and M. Bhuvaneshwari[1]. The *cosplitting graph* $CS(G)$ obtained from G , by adding a new vertex w for each vertex $v \in V$ and joining w to those vertices of G which are not adjacent to v in G . For example, a graph G and its cosplitting graph $CS(G)$ are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4

In a similar way, $[CS(G)]_v$ denotes the neighbourhood contracted graph with respect to v in a cosplitting graph $CS(G)$. Note that $CS(G_v)$ denotes the cosplitting graph of the contracted graph G_v of G . For example, the graph G_{v_1} , $CS(G_{v_1})$ and $[CS(G)]_{v_1}$ for the Figure 4 are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5

In this paper, we discuss about the relation between neighbourhood contraction in $S(G)$ and $CS(G)$ with the splitting and cosplitting graphs of the contracted graphs respectively. Also, we construct n non isomorphic graphs with isomorphic neighbourhood contracted graphs.

2. Main Results:

Proposition 2.1: For any connected graph G , $[S(G)]_{v_1} \cong [S(G)]_{v_1'}$.

Proof: Let G be a graph and $S(G)$ be its splitting graph. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $V(S(G)) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, v_1', v_2', \dots, v_n'\}$ be the vertex set of G and $S(G)$ respectively. Let v_i' be the corresponding newly added vertex to v_i for all $1 \leq i \leq n$ in $S(G)$. $N(v_1') = \{v_i / d(v_1', v_i) = 1\}$. But $N(v_1) = \{v_i, v_i' / d(v_1, v_i) = 1\}$. Then, $N(v_1) = N(v_1') \cup \{v_i' / d(v_1, v_i) = 1\}$. Therefore, $N(v_1') \subsetneq N(v_1)$. Hence, $[S(G)]_{v_1'}$ has more vertices compared to $[S(G)]_{v_1}$.

Therefore, $[S(G)]_{v_1} \not\cong [S(G)]_{v_1'}$.

Figure 6 shows the illustration of the above proposition.

Figure 6

Theorem 2.2: Let G be a graph and $CS(G)$ be its cosplitting graph. If v is a full vertex of G , then $G \subseteq [CS(G)]_{v'}$.

Proof: Let G be a graph and v be a full vertex in G . Let $CS(G)$ be its cosplitting graph and v' be the newly added vertex in $CS(G)$ corresponding to v in G . Since v is a full vertex in G , by definition v' is a pendant vertex in $CS(G)$. Also, $N_{CS(G)}(v) = N_G(v) \cup \{v'\}$. Now in $CS(G)$, $N_2(v') = N_{CS(G)}(v) \setminus \{v'\} = N_G(v) \setminus v'$. Hence $[CS(G)]_{v'} \subseteq (CS(G)) \setminus \{v'\}$. Since $G \subseteq CS(G)$, we get $G \subseteq [CS(G)]_{v'}$.

Figure 7 shows the illustration of this theorem.

Figure 7

Theorem 2.3: For any graph G , there exist n graphs, $n \geq 2$, G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n such that $G, G_i \not\cong G_j$ for $i \neq j$ and $(G_i)_v \cong (G_j)_v \cong G \vee K_1$ and $\langle N(v) \rangle$ is independent in each G_i .

Proof: Let G be any graph. Construct a graph $H_i = G \circ K_i^c, 1 \leq i \leq n$. It is obvious that $H_i \not\cong H_j, i \neq j, 1 \leq i, j \leq n$. Now construct G_i from H_i such that $V(G_i) = V(H_i) \cup \{v\}, E(G_i) = E(H_i) \cup \{uv / d(u) = 1 \text{ in } H_i\}$. Since $H_i \not\cong H_j$, it can be easily verified that $G_i \not\cong G_j$, for all $i \neq j$. It is easy to note that $\langle N(v) \rangle$ is independent in each G_i . And in G_i , the neighbour of v are all pendant vertices in H_i . Since $H_i \cong G \circ K_i^c$, no vertex of G can be a pendant vertex in H_i . So, the vertices of G remain unaltered in $(G_i)_v$. Now in $(G_i)_v$, all pendant vertices of H_i are deleted and neighbours of all pendant vertices of H_i are made adjacent to v in $(G_i)_v$. Every vertex of G is adjacent to a pendant vertex in H_i . Therefore, $(G_i)_v \cong G \vee K_1$, for all $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Figure 8 illustrates the above theorem, for the case $n=2$.

Figure 8

Note that the above constructed graph is not unique with this property. Next theorem shows another construction for n non isomorphic graphs G_i such that $(G_i)_v \cong G \vee K_1$, for all $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $\langle N(v) \rangle$ is complete.

Theorem 2.4: For any given graph G and any positive integer n , there exists n graphs $n \geq 2, G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ such that $G_i \not\cong G_j$, for all $i \neq j$ and $1 \leq i, j \leq n$ and $(G_i)_v \cong (G_j)_v \cong G \vee K_1$, for all $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $\omega(G_i) \leq \omega(G_j)$, for all $i \leq j, 1 \leq i, j \leq n$.

Proof: Let G be any graph. Construct a graph $H_i = G \vee K_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ with $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_i\}$ be the vertices of K_i . It is obvious that $H_i \not\cong H_j$, for every $i \neq j, 1 \leq i, j \leq n$. Now construct G_i from H_i such that $V(G_i) = V(H_i) \cup \{v\}, E(G_i) = E(H_i) \cup \{u_j v / 1 \leq j \leq i\}$ where $1 \leq i \leq n$. Since $H_i \not\cong H_j$, it can be easily verified that $G_i \not\cong G_j$, for all $i \neq j$. And in $G_i, \langle N(v) \rangle \cong K_i$. Since $H_i = G \vee K_i$, no vertex of G can be a pendant vertex in H_i . So, vertices of G remain unaltered in $(G_i)_v$. In fact, $(G_i)_v = G \vee K_1$. Now note that $\omega(G_i) = \omega(G) + i$. Hence we get $\omega(G_i) \leq \omega(G_j)$, for

all $i \leq j, 1 \leq i, j \leq n$.

Figure 9 shows the illustration of this theorem.

Figure 9

Also, the theorem can be extended to a method of constructing n non-isomorphic graphs which on contraction yield G itself.

Theorem 2.5: For any given graph G , and any positive integer $n, n \geq 2, G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ such that $G_i \not\cong G_j$, for all $i \neq j$ and $1 \leq i, j \leq n$ and $(G_i)_v \cong (G_j)_v \cong G$.

Proof: Let G be a connected graph. Then there exists a vertex u in G such that $uv \in E(G)$. Now, construct a multigraph H_i from G by replacing uv by i multiedges, $1 \leq i \leq n$. Now, construct a simple graph G_i from H_i , such that $V(G_i) = V(H_i) \cup \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{d(v)+(i-1)}\}$ and $E(G_i) = E(H_i) \cup \{vw_j, w_ju / u \in N(v)\} \setminus \{vu / u \in N(v)\}$. Also, $N_{G_i}(v) = \{w_j / 1 \leq j \leq d(v) + (i-1)\}$. Hence in $G_i, N_2(v) = N_G(v)$. Therefore, $(G_i)_v \cong G$, for all $1 \leq i \leq n$. Hence the proof. Figure 10 shows the illustration of this theorem.

Figure 10

Theorem 2.6: For any two given graphs G and H , there exist n non isomorphic graphs G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n such that $G_i \not\cong G_j$, for all $i \neq j$ and $1 \leq i, j \leq n$ and $(G_i)_v \cong G \vee K_1$, and $\langle N(v) \rangle = iH$, for any $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, where $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Proof: Let G and H be any graph. Construct a graph $H_i = G \circ (iH)$, $1 \leq i \leq n$. It is obvious that $H_i \not\cong H_j$, for every $i \neq j$, $1 \leq i, j \leq n$. Now construct a graph G_i from H_i such that $V(G_i) = V(H_i) \cup \{v\}$ and $E(G_i) = E(H_i) \cup \{uv / u \in H\}$. Since $H_i \not\cong H_j$, it can be easily verified that $G_i \not\cong G_j$, for all $i \neq j$. It is easy to note that $\langle N(v) \rangle = iH$, $1 \leq i \leq n$. And no vertex of G is adjacent to v in G_i . So, the vertices of G remain unaltered in $(G_i)_v$. Now in $(G_i)_v$, the vertices of iH are deleted and the neighbours of iH are made adjacent to v in $(G_i)_v$. Every vertex of G is adjacent to a copy of H . Therefore, $(G_i)_v \cong G \vee K_1$.

Figure 11 illustrates the above theorem for the case $n = 2$.

Figure 11

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